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Water and Irrigation Requirement for Summer Rice Crop of North Eastern Coastal Plain Zone of Odisha

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Abstract

Due to continuous increase in population, the water demand and utilization have increased significantly. Rainfall is a limited source for productive agriculture in the province. But the sustainable management and use of water resources for food production is an important issue. So water requirement of crops was also an important part. Water used by crops is predominantly lost by transpiration (T) but there are also evaporative (E) losses from the soil and from plant surfaces. Crop water requirement is defined as the depth of water needed to meet the water losses through evapotranspiration (ET) of a disease free crop, growing in large fields under non restricting soil conditions including soil water and fertility while achieving full production potential under the given growing environment. Evapotranspiration is important to evaluate the irrigation potentialities of various agricultural zones and helps improve the practices of water management and crop production. The crop water requirement (CWR) and irrigation requirement (IR) of various crops were calculated using CROPWAT 8.0. Relevant crop coefficients (Kc), duration of crops and cropping pattern were used to calculate CWR from ETo. These coefficients present the relationship between references (ETo) and crop evapotranspiration (ET crop) or $ET\ crop = Kc * ETo$. Value of Kc varies with the crop, its stage of growth, growing season and the prevailing weather conditions. ET crop or CWR can be determined in mm per day. Water (ETc) and irrigation requirement of summer rice is 853mm and 661mm respectively

Key words: Water Irrigation Requirement, Rice.

Introduction

Agriculture is the major user of water, improving agricultural water management is essential. Generally, the yield decreased by 50% due to water stress. Efficient agricultural water management requires reliable estimation of crop water requirement. Crop need available water sufficiently and at the right time during its growth stages. Because economically crop production has direct relationship with irrigation. However, irrigation scheduling has been based on the predicted crop water requirements (CWR). Which is the amount of water needed to supply its evapotranspiration needs from planting to harvest for a given crop in a specific climate regime? When adequate soil water is maintained by rainfall and/or irrigation, it does not limit plant growth and crop yield (Hess, 2005). CWR is calculated for a given crop under the different climatic conditions. (FAO, 2005) defined that CWR is the depth (or amount) of water needed to meet the water loss through evapotranspiration. The crop water require-

ment always refers to a crop grown under optimal conditions, i.e. a uniform crop, actively growing, completely shading the ground, free of diseases, and favorable soil conditions (including fertility and water).

The continuing growth of world population places new demands on water resources every day. A water shortage has become serious problem. So Improved management and planning of water resources are needed to ensure proper use and distribution of water among competing users. Accurate planning and delivery of the necessary amount of water in time and space can conserve water. The primary objective of irrigation is to apply water to maintain crop Evapotranspiration (ETc) when precipitation is insufficient. Each and every crop has individual water requirements. Net irrigation water requirement (NIWR) is the quantity of water necessary for crop growth.

Equation to analyze crop water requirements in mm day⁻¹ (ETc),

is $E_{Tc} = K_c \times E_{To}$, in which K_c is crop coefficient, E_{To} is reference evapotranspiration (mm day^{-1}). Reference crop evapotranspiration (E_{To}) plays an important role in estimating the net irrigation requirement of crops for agricultural planning, irrigation scheduling. Accurate estimate of E_{To} is a key component in hydrological studies. E_{To} depends on several climatologically factors, such as temperature, humidity, wind speed, radiation, type and stage of growth of the crop etc.

It is necessary to know the crop water requirements for different regions to meet the irrigation demand and for sustainable development of agriculture. One of the major practices adopted by the researchers for water requirement of crops is modeling. For determination of crop evapotranspiration and yield responses to water, CROPWAT model is used which was developed by Smith of the FAO Land and Water Development Division. It is a practical tool (software) used to help agro meteorologists, agronomists and irrigation engineers to carry out standard calculations for evapotranspiration and crop water use studies, and more accurate design and management for irrigation schemes. It is one of the models that are being extensively used in the field of water management throughout the world. CROPWAT facilitates the estimation of the crop evapotranspiration, crop water requirements and irrigation schedule with different cropping patterns for irrigation planning. Based on FAO Penman-Monteith method. It requires some input meteorological parameter like maximum temperature, minimum temperature, relative humidity, sunshine hour, wind speed. After putting all the input parameters, it calculates reference evapotranspiration, effective rainfall, crop evapotranspiration and irrigation requirement for the North Eastern Coastal Plain Zone of Odisha.

Beyazgu et al. (2000) [1] studied an inter-comparison on evapotranspiration (ET), six methods for estimating the reference ET had been applied on a cotton field in the Gediz Basin, Turkey. Irmak et al. (2003)[4] compared the performances of solar and net radiation based methods with other methods. The performance of the derived equations was evaluated for 6 years (1995-2000) including dry and wet years, for the same site and for other humid locations in the Southeast United States. Cai et al. (2007) [3] studied on real-time irrigation management and water resources allocation that needs real-time prediction of daily reference evapotranspiration (E_{To}). Yin et al. [5](2008) calibrated the empirical equation to estimate radiation by taking observed solar radiation of 81 meteorological stations over China during (1971- 2000). Bouraima et al. (2015) [2] paper estimated the crop reference and actual evapotranspiration (E_{To} and E_{Tc}) respectively, and the irrigation water requirement of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) in Benin's sub-basin of the Niger River (BSBNR) of west Africa, using CROPWAT model.

The aim of present study is to estimate the crop water and the irrigation requirement of major crops by using CROPWAT software. This software first calculates E_{To} value and effective rainfall, which is necessary for estimation of CWR and IR. Keeping the above in view, the following objectives are selected for this study.

Objectives of the Study

Estimation of water requirement and irrigation requirement of rice for North Eastern Coastal Plain zone of Odisha.

Materials and Methods

Study Area North Eastern Coastal Plain zone is taken as the study area for this study. Which latitude is $21^{\circ} 06' N$ and longitude is $86^{\circ} 50' E$. This zone has 3 districts - Balasore, Bhadrak and Jajpur. The research station is in this zone is located at Ranital, Bhadrak district (Figure 1) The effective rainfall was calculated with CROPWAT by using the USDA Soil Conservation Method. The CWR and IR value was also calculated. Crop water and irrigation requirement for major crops grown in three seasons, kharif (medium duration paddy, short duration paddy, and summer (rice) of the all agro-climatic zones were calculated. Accurate estimation of crop water and irrigation requirement helps to achieve the sustainable water utilization by

Figure 1. Experimental Site

the farmers. A model was found out, by using the model a farmer of this zone can find out the water requirement and the irrigation requirement by giving the crop name according to their season and duration of crop.

Effective Rainfall Estimation

For effective rainfall calculation, rainfall data records from a range of years (2005-13) were collected from the nearest climatic research station. Then rainfall data were imported into CROPWAT model, which automatically estimated values of effective rainfall.

CWR and IR Estimation

For CWR and IR estimation, crop data and soil data along with climate data were collected from FAO56, irrigation book and field. CWR and IR of major crop season wise are calculated by this model.

Result and Discussion

The mean monthly E_{To} value shows that it is highest in the month of May (6.2 mm/day) due to the summer season and lowest during the month 3.02 mm/day for the winter season.

CWR and IR Value of Summer Crop

Water requirement value is generally highest then the a irrigation requirement and effective rainfall value, because the summation of irrigation requirement and effective rainfall is water requirement. Water (E_{Tc}) and irrigation requirement of summer rice is 853 mm and 661 mm respectively (Table 1, 2)

Conclusion

Water (E_{Tc}) and irrigation requirement of summer rice is 853 mm and 661 mm respectively.

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Table 1. ETo Value of Different Months from 2005 to 2013.

Month	ET0									
	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	Avg.
January	3.21	2.9	2.73	2.99	3.11	3.08	3.25	2.93	2.97	3.02
February	4.07	4.23	3.23	3.39	3.72	4.46	3.87	4.18	3.81	3.88
March	4.8	5.09	4.84	4.6	5.05	5.89	5.29	5.47	5.36	5.15
April	6.01	6.12	5.89	5.86	5.68	7.03	5.69	6.15	6.21	6.07
May	6.39	5.72	5.88	6.44	5.96	6.84	5.94	6.73	5.89	6.2
June	5.24	4.37	4.19	3.98	4.79	5.79	5.27	6.27	5.38	5.03
July	4.13	3.73	3.99	4.14	3.6	5.12	5.04	4.99	4.88	4.4
August	3.81	3.12	4.23	4.19	4.44	4.78	4.52	4.73	4.87	4.3
September	3.87	3.87	3.33	3.74	3.98	4.37	4.14	4.4	4.25	3.99
October	3.79	4.25	4.46	4.23	4.07	4.12	4.56	4.35	3.63	4.16
November	4	2.95	4.04	3.78	3.85	3.79	4.12	3.44	3.72	3.74
December	2.85	3.13	2.77	2.82	2.89	3.2	3.49	3.17	3.35	3.07
Avg.	4.34	4.12	4.13	4.18	4.26	4.87	4.6	4.73	4.53	4.42

Table 2. ETo Value of Different Months from 2005 to 2013

Crop Name	ETc, mm	Effective rainfall, mm	Irr. Req., mm
Rice 150	853	425	661